

Uncertainty Quantification of MHD Flows in Fusion Reactors using a Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition

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ABSTRACT

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) is a theory that describes electrically conducting fluids, widely exploited in magnetic confinement fusion for modeling the dynamics of liquid metals flowing in the blanket of many proposed tokamak designs. The numerical resolution of MHD models typically requires solving nonlinear, coupled equations, which require extremely high computational costs. These costs make large-scale parametric analyses or uncertainty quantification (UQ) studies practically infeasible when relying on full-order numerical models. This work employs a Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) framework based on the parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) approach to enable efficient uncertainty analyses of MHD flows. The study relies on an already developed and tested parametric surrogate model that reconstructs the system dynamics over a range of magnetic field intensities, allowing rapid evaluation of MHD dynamics for different samples of the input magnetic field. The proposed approach is applied to a benchmark configuration of compressible lead–lithium flow in a heated channel under different magnetic field intensities, representative of fusion blanket physics. The results demonstrate that the reduced model can be effectively employed to perform large-scale parametric uncertainty quantification analyses. By drastically reducing the computational cost compared to full-order simulations, the ROM framework enables the propagation of input uncertainties and the evaluation of global sensitivity indices over thousands of parametric realizations, which would be otherwise computationally prohibitive. The study highlights the potential of ROM strategies as a key enabler for uncertainty quantification in magnetohydrodynamic systems relevant to fusion technology.

Keywords: Fusion Reactor Blanket, Uncertainty Quantification, Magnetohydrodynamics, Reduced Order Modeling, Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition

1. INTRODUCTION

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) theory investigates the behavior of electrically conducting fluids that interact with magnetic fields and represents a key aspect in magnetic confinement fusion [1], particularly in the analysis and design of reactor components in which liquid metals [2] or metallic molten salts [3] are foreseen, such as blankets. In such configurations, the presence of the magnetic field may strongly affect both flow dynamics and heat transfer processes, ultimately influencing the overall performance and safety of the system. Capturing and quantifying these magnetically induced effects requires solving a system of coupled, nonlinear equations [4] that govern the evolution of velocity, pressure, and temperature within the conducting medium under the effect of a magnetic field. While full-order models (FOM) can describe the underlying coupled physics with a high degree of accuracy, their

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computational costs become prohibitive when extensive parametric explorations or uncertainty quantification (UQ) studies are needed. Variations in the magnetic field intensity and profile across reactor components can substantially alter the thermal–hydraulic response, yet evaluating these effects through full-order simulations would require thousands of runs, making a purely high-fidelity approach computationally impractical even on powerful machines.

Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) [5] offers an efficient alternative to FOMs in the context of multi-query simulations by constructing surrogate models that approximate the FOM dynamics at a fraction of the computational cost. In essence, ROM methods project or interpolate the system behavior onto a low-dimensional manifold while preserving the essential physical behavior. Thus, ROM techniques build a low-dimensional surrogate model that enables the efficient exploration of parametric spaces and the execution of extensive parametric analyses, making it suitable for real-time and design-oriented applications in fusion technology. Within the MHD field for nuclear fusion, the application of ROM techniques is still in its early stages [6, 7, 8, 9], especially for scenarios involving electrically conducting liquid metals [10, 11].

This work relies on a reduced model previously developed by the authors ([12]) and tested for MHD flows in blanket-relevant configurations to exploit the ROM approach to perform a global uncertainty quantification analysis with respect to variations in the applied magnetic field. In this study, the parameter under consideration is represented by the magnetic field intensity. The adopted approach combines a parametric reduced order model, based on the Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD), with a Monte Carlo sampling of the input magnetic field intensity. The reduced model allows the generation of a large ensemble of system states for different magnetic configurations, enabling the statistical characterization of their spatial and temporal variability. The main objective of this study is to demonstrate that surrogate models can make feasible large-scale uncertainty analyses that would otherwise be computationally unaffordable using full-order models. To the best of the authors knowledge, this work represents the first attempt to employ a parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition for uncertainty quantification analyses. The results demonstrate that surrogate models can make such analyses computationally feasible, achieving a speed-up of over four orders of magnitude compared to full-order simulations. The proposed approach is generic and extendable to different parameters and also for different reactors configurations. This represents a key step towards the integration of MHD reduced models into design optimization for fusion reactor components.

2. PARAMETRIC DYNAMIC MODE DECOMPOSITION

The Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) [13] is a data-driven, non-intrusive reduced order modeling technique that constructs a linear surrogate model from a set of full-order solutions (called snapshots), without requiring access to the governing equations. DMD decomposes the snapshots into spatially correlated modes, each associated with a single temporal behavior, such as oscillations or exponential growth/decay. By ranking these modes according to the singular values of the snapshot matrix, which broadly speaking indicates the percentage information content of each mode, DMD generates a low-dimensional linear model capable of approximating the temporal evolution of the system. Essentially, DMD combines the strengths of Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) in space with Fourier-like analysis in time, providing a highly interpretable representation of complex dynamics. The optimized variant OptDMD [14], implemented in [12], improves robustness and accuracy by fitting an exponential model to the snapshot data directly.

Parametric extensions of DMD allow generalization across multiple parameter configurations. Multiple snapshot matrices corresponding to different parametric realizations are projected onto a reduced space via Singular Value Decomposition, yielding latent dynamics in a compressed representation. OptDMD is then applied in this reduced space to efficiently compute modes, frequencies, and amplitudes. A regression model maps the parameter values to these DMD quantities, enabling the reconstruction of surrogate models for new, unseen parametric realizations. This approach, known as Reduced Koopman

Operators Interpolation (rKOI) [15], permits rapid, accurate predictions of high-dimensional dynamics for arbitrary input values while drastically reducing computational costs.

This parametric approach has been employed in [12] for the study of a magnetohydrodynamic lead-lithium flow in a dimensional channel. In the present work, the obtained surrogate model is leveraged to perform an extensive uncertainty quantification analysis with respect to variations in the input parameter, namely the intensity of the applied magnetic field.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The MHD scenario considered in [12] and used in this work consists of a magnetohydrodynamic flow of lead-lithium flowing in a two-dimensional channel subjected to a vertical constant and uniform magnetic field. The channel geometry includes two cold steps on the top wall and one hot step on the bottom wall (for more details on the benchmark characteristics, refer to [12]). A visual representation of the geometry is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Lead-lithium MHD benchmark investigated in [12] and considered in this work.

The compressible, viscoresistive lead-lithium flow in the selected geometry has been represented by the MHD model [16] reported below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll}
 \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \rho (\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} = -\nabla p + \rho \vec{g} + \mu \Delta \vec{u} + \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times \vec{B} \right) \times \vec{B} & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho c_p (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) T = \kappa \Delta T & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \rho = \rho_0 (1 - \beta (T - T_0)) & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) + \frac{1}{\sigma \mu_0} \Delta \vec{B} & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, t > 0 \\
 \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}, T = T_0, \rho = \rho_0, \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_0 & \text{in } \Omega, t = 0 \\
 \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_{in} & \text{on } \Gamma_{inlet}, t > 0 \\
 \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_{outlet}, t > 0 \\
 \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} & \text{on } \Gamma_{walls}, t > 0 \\
 \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_0 & \text{on } \Gamma_{walls}, t > 0 \\
 \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_{inlet} \cup \Gamma_{outlet}, t > 0 \\
 p = p_{out} & \text{on } \Gamma_{outlet}, t > 0 \\
 \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 & \text{on } \partial \Omega \setminus \Gamma_{outlet}, t > 0 \\
 T = T_{top} & \text{on } \Gamma_{top\ steps}, t > 0 \\
 T = T_{bottom} & \text{on } \Gamma_{bottom\ step}, t > 0
 \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where Ω is the domain, $\partial \Omega$ the entire boundary, Γ are the surfaces of the boundary and t is the time. Moreover, \mathbf{u} represents the fluid velocity, p the pressure, \mathbf{B} the magnetic field, ρ the density, T the tem-

perature, \mathbf{g} the gravity, μ the dynamic viscosity, μ_0 the magnetic permeability and σ the electrical conductivity, κ the thermal conductivity, c_p the specific heat. All the details on the physical and numerical parameters are reported in Table I.

Table I. Physical and numerical parameters for the lead-lithium flow.

ρ_0	9806 kg/m ³	κ	20.93 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	L	0.2 m
μ	1.93e-3 Pa · s	u_{in}	0.0492 m/s	H	0.02 m
μ_0	1.26e-6 H/m	p_{out}	10 ⁵ Pa	H_1	0.006 m
σ	7.82e5 Ω ⁻¹ m ⁻¹	T_0	600 K	H_2	0.008 m
β	1.3e-4 K ⁻¹	T_{top}	550 K	n° cells	14460
c_p	189.5 Jkg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	T_{bottom}	650 K	z	1e-4 m (1 cell)

Multiple simulations corresponding to different values of the magnetic field intensity were performed up to 3 seconds of simulation time ($B_0 \in \mathcal{B} = [0.01, 0.5]$ T). These data were generated exploiting the MHD library *magnetoHDFoam* for OpenFOAM, developed and presented in [17] and publicly available under the MIT license at <https://github.com/ERMETE-Lab/MHD-magnetoHDFoam>.

The resulting full-order snapshots served as the training set for the parametric DMD model, which has been presented in [12]. The obtained surrogate model was shown to accurately reconstruct the system state for a magnetic field value within the parameter range, but not included in the training data. In particular, the pDMD reconstruction was directly compared with the corresponding full-order solution computed at that parameter value, showing very small and spatially localized differences. Moreover, the relative L^2 -error between the full-order solution and the pDMD reconstruction was below 2% for both temperature and pressure fields, further confirming the accuracy of the reduced-order model. The present work employs this verified reduced model to perform a parametric uncertainty quantification analysis with respect to variations in the magnetic field intensity.

1000 realizations of the magnetic field intensity were generated using a Monte Carlo sampling approach. The field B was assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution with mean $\bar{B}_0 = 0.3$ T and standard deviation equal to 5% of its mean value. The mean value of 0.3 T was selected as it corresponds to the magnetic field intensity for which the reduced model had been tested in [12], demonstrating high accuracy in reproducing the system dynamics. Figure 2 shows the obtained distribution.

Figure 2. Distribution of the samples of the magnetic field intensity obtained through a Monte Carlo approach.

This probabilistic description may represent the uncertainty associated with the magnetic field felt by the fluid. Each sampled value of the magnetic field was then used as input for the reduced model, which provided the corresponding lead-lithium temperature and pressure fields as outputs. As the reduced model was trained using scaled data, the predicted outputs are expressed in adimensional form, normalized according to a min-max scaling procedure. From the 1000 ROM realizations, the mean temperature and pressure fields were computed at each point in the space-time domain, together with their corresponding standard deviations.

Figure 3. Spatial profile of the mean of temperature (a) and pressure (b) and standard deviation of temperature (c) and pressure (d) fields across the 1000 realizations for $t = 2.5$ s. Temporal profile of the global mean and maximum standard deviation for the temperature (e) and pressure (f) fields.

Figure 3 shows the spatial profile of the means (μ_T and μ_p) and the standard deviations (σ_T and σ_p) across the 1000 obtained outputs for both the fields at a selected time instant. The mean fields provide a representation of the average profile for the considered range of magnetic field intensities, while the standard deviations quantify the local variability. These calculations provide local information on the spatial distribution of output variability, highlighting the regions of the domain that are most sensitive to magnetic field variations, which are the areas near the steps. Figure 3 also reports the temporal evolution of the spatially averaged and maximum standard deviation values. The maximum standard deviations remain considerably lower than the relative standard deviation 5% imposed on the magnetic field intensity (below 0.018 for the temperature and 0.009 for the pressure). Thus, the system response exhibits a damped sensitivity to variations in B_0 .

Furthermore, to quantify the sensitivity of the system outputs to variations in the magnetic field, a

relative sensitivity coefficient is introduced, defined as:

$$S_T(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\sigma_T(\mathbf{x}, t) / \mu_T(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\sigma_B / \mu_B}, \quad S_p(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\sigma_p(\mathbf{x}, t) / \mu_p(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\sigma_B / \mu_B}, \quad (2)$$

where μ_B and σ_B are the mean and standard deviation of the 1000 samples of magnetic field used as input. The magnetic field intensity was normalized using the same min-max scaling applied to temperature and pressure, ensuring a consistent comparison between input and output uncertainties within the dimensionless framework of the analysis.

The introduced coefficient measures the relative amplification or attenuation of input uncertainties in the output fields. Values of $S > 1$ indicate regions where the output variability is amplified with respect to the input uncertainty, whereas $S < 1$ indicates damping. In this way, S provides both a local indicator that identifies spatial regions where the system is particularly sensitive to magnetic field fluctuations and a temporal global measure of sensitivity (by averaging over space). Figure 4 shows the spatial distribution of the sensitivity coefficient for a selected time instant, together with the temporal evolution of the spatially averaged and spatially maximum values.

Figure 4. Spatial profile of the sensitivity coefficient for the temperature (a) and pressure (c) for $t = 2.5$ s and global coefficient sensitivity for temperature (b) and pressure (d).

The results show that S always remains below unity, indicating that the output variability is attenuated compared to the input uncertainty. The maximum sensitivity reaches about 0.60 for temperature and 0.15 for pressure, revealing a stronger but still moderate influence of magnetic field variations on the thermal field. Spatially, the highest variations are localized after the steps, while the temporal trends confirm the overall robustness of the system to magnetic field perturbations.

The results obtained in this work highlight that, for the considered MHD configuration, the system response tends to attenuate the input uncertainty associated with variations in the magnetic field intensity. However, this outcome is strongly problem-dependent: different geometrical setups, boundary

conditions, or flow regimes could exhibit significantly different responses. Indeed, the MHD dynamics of lead–lithium are highly sensitive to the specific magnetic field felt by the fluid, and variations in both the intensity and the spatial–temporal distribution can induce very different MHD effects, potentially altering the overall flow behavior and operating regime.

Therefore, developing reliable methods to quantify the variability induced by such magnetic field fluctuations is essential to ensure the safe operation of liquid metal systems and also to guarantee their stable performance within blanket components of fusion reactors. This underlines the importance of having quick tools for systematically performing uncertainty and sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of MHD systems. Such analyses would be computationally prohibitive without a reduced-order modeling framework, since a singular resolution of the full-order model in this scenario would require approximately 20 min on an HPC cluster, whereas 1000 realizations with the reduced-order model took less than 1 min. This corresponds to a computational speed-up of more than four orders of magnitude, demonstrating the remarkable efficiency and potential of the ROM approach for large-scale parametric and uncertainty quantification studies in complex MHD applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a reduced-order modeling approach based on parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) has been employed to perform an uncertainty quantification analysis of a magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) scenario. The reduced model, previously developed and verified, was employed to propagate uncertainty in the applied magnetic field intensity through 1000 Monte Carlo realizations. The results show that, for the considered configuration, the uncertainty in the input (magnetic field intensity) is attenuated in the outputs of the system (temperature and pressure). This indicates that magnetic field variations have a relatively moderate impact on the global system behavior. This analysis was made possible by employing the ROM approach, which enabled the exploration of a large scale of system responses while drastically lowering the computational cost compared to full-order simulations. Beyond the computational advantage, the ROM framework also enabled a spatially resolved uncertainty analysis, revealing the regions that are the most affected by magnetic field fluctuations.

However, the obtained results are related to the specific MHD configuration considered in this work, and results may differ under alternative geometries, flow regimes, or magnetic field profiles. The MHD dynamics of lead–lithium are strongly influenced by the specific magnetic field experienced by the fluid: different field intensities or shapes can generate substantially different flow and thermal responses. Quantifying this variability is therefore essential to ensure the safe and reliable operation of liquid metal systems in fusion blankets. However, generating such a large ensemble of simulations would be computationally infeasible with a full-order model, whereas this work proves that the surrogate models allow the analysis to drastically reduce the computational burden. Future works may focus on applying this methodology to more complex and realistic MHD configurations, considering also multiple uncertain parameters, and coupled multi-physics scenarios relevant to fusion reactor design and optimization.

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